

DEVELOPMENT OF A FAST DRAPING ALGORITHM USING MULTIFACTORIAL SIMULATIONS OF LOCAL SHEAR

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Keywords: Draping Simulations, Woven Fabric, In-Plane Shearing, Base Surfaces

ABSTRACT

Designing draping strategies for industrial LCM preforms requires a significant amount of time and testing. Using predictive software tools for probing multiple draping scenarios accelerates the identification of an ideal draping strategy for different mould surfaces. Mould surfaces are defined by a number of geometric features labelled base surfaces, which are identified in CAD models. These base surfaces lead to specific in-plane shear behaviour in the textile reinforcements on the full mould. Using vertex coordinates and edge lengths available in CAD models, a multi-parameter remodelling tool – the conical frustum – is used for quantifying the base surfaces and building a database of in-plane shear results. Taguchi plans assist in limiting the number of simulations required to populate the database and provide methods for interpolating the results. The predictive tool probes the database, linking the results and determining a draping strategy. By investigating the in-plane shear behaviour of individual base surfaces and linking them, numerous draping scenarios can be developed and probed quickly. From these scenarios a favourable draping strategy can be determined. This paper outlines the process by which the database is built, how localized shear results interact between neighbouring base surfaces, and how an algorithm for probing scenarios can be used when developing different draping strategies.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Preforming scenarios and the search for the best strategy

Liquid moulding composite (LCM) manufacturing processes such as Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM), Vacuum-Assisted Resin Transfer Moulding (VARTM) and Resin Film Infusion (RFI) require that textile reinforcements be draped into preforms, over complex mould surfaces. Identifying the best draping strategy, which allows for swift and reproducible production of these preforms, requires the probing of multiple draping scenarios. A scenario is the ensemble of steps that are required for covering a mould surface and producing a preform, typically from more than one pattern or piece of fabric. The strategy is the best scenario, which must be identified. Designing strategies for industrial cases is complex, as it includes consideration of darting, multiple patterns, small radii, sharp corners, etc., thus the need to probe multiple scenarios. In view of the large number of draping parameters such as starting position, starting orientation, number of distinct patterns used, pre-existing in-plane shear and others, identifying the best scenario is challenging. Engineers and technicians with significant practical experience of draping can conduct lengthy trial and error development work in the rare cases where the physical mould is readily available. In reality, they will only test and probe a small fraction of all possible scenarios and settle on a scenario that works, although it may not be the best one. Such work becomes considerably more difficult when the physical mould is not available. Replacing trials with simulation becomes appealing as this enables the examination of draping scenarios. With access to CAD models of the parts or moulds, draping simulations investigating in-plane shear can be performed, assisting in probing different scenarios. Software packages exist that can simulate draping, but they suffer from similar limitations: they enable arbitrary probing of scenarios and the identification of a few scenarios that may work, but they do not guarantee the identification of the best scenario, or strategy.

1.2 Surface types, draping parameters and database of shear results

Mould surfaces consist of geometric features that can be flat, single curvature, double curvature and twisted surfaces. These features, labelled base surfaces, control the extent of in-plane shear generated when draping the fabric. Base surfaces are identified and quantified using vertices and common edges available in CAD models of the moulds. Geometric parameters are discussed in section 2.1 of this paper. Draping parameters such as fibre starting orientation, starting position, pre-existing in-plane shear at entry and others are also considered. Shear results are contained in a database that is structured around base surfaces and draping parameters as inputs (Figure 1). Draping parameters are discussed in section 2.2 of this paper.

Figure 1: Representation of database contents

1.3 Conical Frustum

In order to structure the database of shear results and populate it prior to using it with any specific mould, a multi-parameter tool for remodeling base surfaces was devised: the conical frustum. Shear results are featured in the database as a function of 12 conical frustum geometric parameters, and additional draping parameters. When probing an actual mould, the coordinates of the vertices as well as dimensions such as lengths and radii are available for each base surface from the CAD model of the mould. The database enables interpolations between shear result entries and it features shear and orientation data as outputs. Parameters from each specific base surface as defined on a specific mould are used for interrogating and interpolating between results available in the database. The conical frustum is discussed in section 2.1 of this paper.

1.4 Structuring the database: Taguchi simulation plans

An unlimited array of in-plane shear results could potentially be generated from the conical frustum geometric parameters and draping parameters through draping simulations performed on base surfaces. To structure the draping simulations and reduce their number whilst retaining the information needed and allow interpolation between results, a Taguchi simulation plan was devised and implemented in populating the database. The consolidation of geometric parameters in order to reduce the number of draping simulations towards database population is presented in Section 2.3 of the paper. The Taguchi plan allows for a set number of simulations to be run and to perform an analysis of which parameters, draping or geometric, have the largest effect on in-plane shear results for each parametrized base surface. Taguchi plans are discussed in sections 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 of this paper.

Using the database of base surface in-plane shear angle and orientation results, different draping scenarios can be probed. Results for each base surface are linked at their common edges and over the entire mould surfaces, leading to different scenarios that may include the use of multiple pieces of fabric

for covering, as well as other techniques used in building complex industrial preforms. The scenarios are refined down to a single draping strategy for the full mould.

This paper focuses on determining which of the geometric and draping parameters have the greatest effect on in-plane shear on base surfaces and on developing an algorithm that uses simulation to determine the best possible draping scenario, ultimately reducing the time required for formulating a draping strategy. These objectives are achieved by building a base surface remodelling tool, the conical frustum, used in conducting shear simulations. Simulation results are conducted and analysed using Taguchi plans in order to determine which parameters have the greatest effect on shearing, and compiled in a database to be used alongside the draping scenario algorithm.

2 INPUT FACTORS FOR BASE SURFACES AND SIMULATIONS

In CAD software, individual base surfaces are separated by shared vertices and common edges. Each base surface is identified as either flat, single curvature, double curvature or twist. Base surfaces are used as a way of modelling the entire mould surface as parameterized pieces, enabling a database to be structured so that the algorithm can look up this database and interpolate between database entries as required by individual base surface parameters, as well as draping parameters. A multi-parameter geometric tool, the conical frustum, was devised, enabling base surfaces to be remodeled and draping simulations to be performed.

2.1 The Conical Frustum – Remodeling Base Surfaces

A classic conical frustum is defined as a portion of a cone that lies between two parallel planes, removing its tip. For the present use as a remodelling tool, modifications to the classic conical frustum were made and parameters were added so that flat, single curvature, double curvature and twisted surfaces may be generated. Rather than using parallel circles, the conical frustum uses ellipses 1 and 2 that can be out of alignment with one another in terms of their major/minor axes and in terms of the planes in which they are defined, Figure 2. Tilt angles θ_1 and θ_2 are specified by vectors \vec{N}_1 and \vec{N}_2 normal to ellipses 1 and 2, and rotation angle α is the angle between the major axis of ellipse 2 projected on ellipse 1 and the major axis of ellipse 1. Finally, straight edges connecting the two ellipses are replaced by radii defined as C_R and C_r , Figure 2.

Figure 2: Conical frustum geometric parameters

Extracted from the CAD file of the mould are six of the conical frustum parameters: the major radii $|R_1|$ and $|R_2|$, minor radii $|r_1|$ and $|r_2|$, and connecting radii C_R and C_r . When examining a base surface on a CAD model, individual edges can be measured within the model, providing length, arc length and/or radii of the edges. As mentioned above, base surfaces forming the mould surface and

identified using vertex coordinates are first translated into a local coordinate system with point D set as the origin. The remaining vertices A , B and C are located at the remaining major and minor radii of the frustum ellipses. Vertices A and B lay on ellipse 1 whilst vertices C and D lay on ellipse 2.

The centre point of each ellipse needs to be calculated in order to determine the magnitude of vector \vec{L} , which points from C_1 to C_2 . For C_1 , Equations 1 and 2 can be combined resulting in two possible solutions for C_1 . Upon calculating C_2 using the same equations, the set of centre points can be compared so that a set of centre points are selected that best represent the base surface being remodeled.

Once the centre points, C_1 and C_2 are known, vectors \vec{R}_1 , \vec{r}_1 , \vec{R}_2 , and \vec{r}_2 can be calculated using Equation 4 and their respective vertex coordinates and ellipse centre points. Finally, sectioning angles β_1 and β_2 are calculated using Equation 2 leading to all 12 parameters identified, Figure 2:

$$|\vec{R}_1| = \sqrt{(X_A - X_1)^2 + (Y_A - Y_1)^2 + (Z_A - Z_1)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$|\vec{r}_1| = \sqrt{(X_B - X_1)^2 + (Y_B - Y_1)^2 + (Z_B - Z_1)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\beta_1 = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\vec{R}_1 \cdot \vec{r}_1}{|\vec{R}_1| |\vec{r}_1|} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\vec{R}_1 = (X_A - X_1, Y_A - Y_1, Z_A - Z_1) \quad (4)$$

where (X_A, Y_A, Z_A) and (X_B, Y_B, Z_B) are the coordinates of vertices A and B , and (X_1, Y_1, Z_1) are the coordinates of centre point C_1 . C_2 is identified by substituting vertex coordinates for A and B with those for C and D . Similarly, β_2 is calculated by substituting the major/minor radii and their magnitudes of ellipse 1 with those of ellipse 2. The 12 geometric parameters are summed up as:

- Major/minor radii for ellipses 1 and 2 $|\vec{R}_1|$, $|\vec{R}_2|$, $|\vec{r}_1|$ and $|\vec{r}_2|$
- Connecting radii C_R and C_r
- Distance between ellipses $|\vec{L}|$
- Sectioning angles β_1 and β_2
- Tilt angles θ_1 and θ_2
- Rotation angle α

2.2 Draping Parameters

Alongside geometric parameters, the four draping parameters used in structuring the shear result database for base surfaces are defined as:

- Starting position P_s
- Starting yarn orientations O_s
- Initial angle between warp and weft (pre-existing shear) ω
- Fibre spacing S

The starting position refers to the entry point where the fabric starts moving into a base surface. When linking multiple surfaces through common edges, starting positions dictate where the fabric goes from one base surface into an adjacent base surface. Starting yarn orientations will vary along a common edge between two base surfaces when shear is observed, Figure 3. Database results are expressed using warp and weft vectors to define orientations along base surface edges, which are used as an adjacent surface is entered, Figure 3. The initial angle between the warp and weft quantifies any pre-existing shear found in a fabric as it enters a base surface. Moving from base surface to base surface will induce in-plane shear, especially when double curvature base surfaces are involved. The change in angle

between warp and weft is known to proceed in a pin-jointed manner [1], rotating about the overlap of warp and weft yarns until a locking angle is reached. Results expressing the behaviour of fabrics that are already sheared prior to moving into an adjacent surface are necessary to produce predictions for multiple adjacent base surfaces. This characteristic is seldom used in draping simulations performed in the traditional way, where one attempts to drape a complete mould all at once in a trial and error simulation procedure. However, it is especially relevant and important in the current approach. Fibre spacing was originally included for completeness, but results presented in Section 3.3 confirmed that this draping parameter does not affect in-plane shear angles or orientations.

Figure 3: Varying starting orientations, starting positions and orientations along a common edge

2.3 Hierarchy of Geometric Parameters

In most cases of industrial geometries, base surfaces can be modelled by changing only some of the geometric parameters listed at the end of Section 2.1. The frustum can be used for modelling any base surface; however, many base surfaces encountered on industrial moulds are relatively simple: flats, filleted edges that correspond to simple sections of straight cylinders, sections of spheres in corners, and so forth. This suggests that many base surfaces can be expressed by varying only some of the geometric parameters of the frustum, while the full list of variable geometric parameters and flexibility of the frustum remain useful in more unique scenarios.

The database was populated by running Taguchi simulation plans where each parameter can take one of two values: a minimum and maximum, as discussed in Section 3.2. Taguchi plans are used because they allow for the total number of combinations ($2^{12} = 4096$ for geometric parameters) to be reduced

without losing critical information. However, some of the geometric parameters are less critical than others as they are used primarily for generating specific cases such as twisted surfaces. Those parameters are α , θ_1 and θ_2 . By further consolidating other parameters the number of geometric parameters can be reduced to five, for a total of $2^5=32$ combinations which is far more manageable whilst retaining the capability to generate most commonly used base surfaces, as explained below.

The tilted ellipses defined in the conical frustum allow for many different surface types to be generated but in many practical, industrial cases the ellipses tend to remain parallel. Setting the major radii $|\overline{R}_1|$ and $|\overline{R}_2|$ equal to the respective minor radii $|\overline{r}_1|$ and $|\overline{r}_2|$, and setting zero values for tilt angles θ_1 and θ_2 restores the circular nature of the classic frustum. Corner fillets and spherical features found on industrial moulds allow C_R and C_r to become equal. Since these cylinders and spherical features tend to simply be a section of a full cylinder or sphere, setting sectioning angles β_1 and β_2 equal further reduces the number of remodeling parameters required in the Taguchi simulation plan. With a number of frustum geometric parameters unchanged for modelling numerous base surfaces, the number of geometric parameters that are actively varied in a reduced Taguchi simulation plan can be lowered to five; $|\overline{R}_1|$, $|\overline{R}_2|$, C_R , β and $|\overline{L}|$. The simplified conical frustum does not eliminate the other seven parameters but consolidates them since they remain unchanged, assisting in populating the database even more efficiently.

3 BUILDING THE DATABASE

3.1. Design of Experiments: Taguchi Simulation Plan

In order to determine which of the geometric and draping parameters have the largest effect on in-plane shear, Taguchi experimental designs were used. Using the simplified conical frustum with five geometric parameters and four draping parameters, simulations for building a database of base surface in-plane shear angles and fibre orientations were conducted using Nottingham Drape It [2]. Whilst the basic frustum is reduced to five geometric parameters in a first version of the database, it can still generate most common base surfaces. The models built using the conical frustum were constructed from individual nodes linked together into triangular elements, Figure 4a. After the draping software ran a simulation, shear angles as well as warp and weft vectors for individual elements were extracted from the draped ply.

Figure 4: a) Remodeled double curvature base surface; b) Draping simulation results

3.2. Input Factors, Responses and Factorial Design

A total of nine two-level factors were chosen for this work, Table 1: the five geometric parameters listed in Section 2.3 and the four draping parameters listed in Section 2.2. Geometric parameter modalities were selected so that flat, single curvature and double curvature features could be represented.

The radius of circle 1, represented as a value of 0 cm, allowed the frustum to build a double curvature corner feature corresponding to a section of a sphere decided by β . Setting $R_1 = R_2$ allowed for single curvature base surfaces to be generated. Setting $C_R = 20$ cm simulates essentially straight connections between the planes of the frustum, resulting in single curvature and flat surfaces.

From the simulation results, maximum, minimum, average and absolute average shear angles were extracted. A positive shear angle refers to angles between warp and weft yarns smaller than 90° , whereas a negative shear angle is the angle between the warp and weft yarns greater than 90° , Figure 5a. The average and absolute average shear angles quantify the total shear over the base surface. When these values are the same, shear over the entire surface is limited. An increase in absolute shear suggests an increase in both positive and negative shear, resulting in more variation in orientation variation along base surface edges, Figure 5b. Alongside shear angles for each surface, warp and weft edge orientation vectors were extracted. These vectors quantify the orientation of the fibres along the edges of the base surfaces.

Figure 5: a) Positive and negative shear; b) Absolute shear

Taguchi Parameter	Parameters	Minimum	Modalities	Maximum
A	Radius of circle 1 $ \overline{R_1} $	0 cm		2 cm
B	Radius of circle 2 $ \overline{R_2} $	1 cm		2 cm
C	Distance between ellipses $ \overline{L} $	0.5 cm		2 cm
D	Radius connecting ellipses C_R	2 cm		20 cm
G	Sectioning angle β	45°		90°
H	Draping starting position P_s	Centre of base surface		Centre of longest edge
K	Starting fibre spacing S	1/20 of longest edge		1/50 of longest edge
M	Angle between warp & weft ω	90°		60° (30° of shear)
N	Starting yarn orientation O_s	0°		45°

Table 1: Taguchi experimental design including parameter modalities

The complete analysis of the nine parameters at two levels would require a total of $2^9 = 512$ separate runs. Achieving this is time consuming, hence a fractional plan featuring specific runs was chosen to assist in hastening the populating of the database. As per Taguchi methodology [3], the resolution of the database can be further increased at a latter point by running more simulations. Using a 16-run two-level Plackett-Burman design with nine modalities adapted from [4] allowed for a first analysis to be performed.

3.3 Results and Discussion

Identifying the parameters that had the largest effect on shear angle was done by using a scree plot of the sum of squares for the parameters. Scree plots for the maximum, minimum, average and absolute average shear angles appear in Figure 6. All plots have the same appearance with parameter M , the initial angle between warp and weft, showing the largest effect on the shear angle, as expected.

Figure 6: Shear angle scree plots: a) Maximum; b) Minimum; c) Average; d) Absolute Average

In order to better observe the effects of the other parameters, removing parameter M from the scree plots revealed that parameters D , G and C all have a significant effect on the shear angle, Figure 7. Parameters D , C and G are all geometric parameters linked to defining the double curvature of base surfaces. The geometric models included in the 16 run plan had eight runs featuring double curvature, six featuring single curvature and two featuring flat surfaces. Parameter D (radius C_R connecting the ellipses) dictated whether flat, single curvature or double curvature surfaces were generated. With more double curvature surfaces featured in the runs, parameter D was observed to have the second largest effect on shear angle. Both parameter G (sectioning angle β), and C (length between ellipses $|\vec{L}|$) increased the surface area of the base surfaces simulated. A larger surface area of double curvature lead to an increase in shear over the surface, resulting in these parameters having a significant effect on shear angle.

Figure 7: Scree plots, M removed: a) Maximum; b) Minimum; c) Average; d) Absolute Average

Results from these simulations presented clear evidence that double curvature surfaces generate shear and that flat and single curvature surfaces do not contribute to shear, as expected. Flat and single curvature surfaces essentially carry any pre-existing shear across their surface until another instance of double curvature is encountered. This observation assisted in reducing the total number of simulations required for populating the database, since shear over surface of these types, as expected, remained constant. Section 4.2 outlines specific cases where variation of shear angle and orientation along base surface edges changes the expected outcome, and it discusses a method for predicting shear on flat and single curvature surfaces in these cases.

4 ALGORITHM FOR PROBING DRAPING SCENARIOS

Given the availability of a database containing in-plane shear and orientation results for parameterized base surfaces, an algorithm was built for predicting draping scenarios and determining a draping strategy. From a mould surface, Figure 8, individual base surfaces within the CAD model are identified. Base surfaces are first labelled and organized alongside corresponding vertices and common edges. Labelling and quantifying all base surface parameters is the first step towards defining interactions that will arise between surfaces of different types. The algorithm determines the order along which the base surfaces are connecting within a given scenario and how shear angles and orientations along each base surface edge are linked.

Figure 8: Mould surface with edges separating base surfaces

4.1 Number of Draping Scenarios

The number of possible draping scenarios that can be generated is dependent on the number of base surfaces and common edges featured on a mould surface. The algorithm probes scenarios by moving between base surfaces individually through common edges. It considers one base surface at a time, interrogating the database and interpolating results for that base surface. Once that surface is analyzed, the algorithm then chooses to interrogate another base surface connected to the previously analyzed surface through a common edge, repeating the process until all base surfaces have been covered or the shear limits of a given piece of fabric have been reached. A single scenario consists of a specific sequence of base surfaces that are linked together as the algorithm moves across the mould surface.

4.2 Varying of Fibre Orientations along an Edge: Shear Progression

Exploring in-plane shear behaviour along connecting edges allows for the algorithm to link results between base surfaces more accurately. Specifically, in some instances involving a double curvature base surface, such as moving from double curvature into single curvature, varying yarn orientations along the common edge lead to a phenomenon labelled shear progression on the adjacent single curvature surface. Typically on single curvature surfaces, in-plane shear is commonly observed to be carried through the surface without change. This is the case when the fabric has constant fibre orientations and shear angles along the entry edge of the base surface, Figure 9a. However, when exiting a double curvature base surface both shear angles and fibre orientations vary along the exit edge, Figure 9b, which leads to shear progression: the continued change of shear angles and fibre orientations as the fabric enters the adjacent single curvature surface, Figure 9c. The fabric continues to shear further over the single curvature surface until it reaches a maximum shear angle at a certain distance from the common edge. Hence, a variation in shear over flat and single curvature surfaces can occur.

Figure 9: Fibre orientations on and beyond common edges: a) Single curvature; b) Double curvature; c) Shear progression

Predicting shear progression can be accomplished using the database results along the connecting edge. Consider a flat base surface with a change in fibre orientations and shear angles along a single edge labelled the common edge, Figure 10. Examining warp yarn orientations along the edge and comparing with a given yarn progressing through the surface, the latter yarn undergoes the same changes in orientation further into the base surface as those seen for other yarns along the edge. Essentially, each change in orientation along the common edge of the base surface is projected onto each of the yarns crossing the common edge. Since there is no shear added within the flat surface as a result of surface topography in the case of flat and single curvature, and no change in orientations along other edges of the surface in the case illustrated, weft yarns remain parallel as the orientations of the warp yarns continue to vary further onto the flat surface.

Figure 10: Projections of orientation change over a flat surface

In the case of a common edge connecting a single curvature surface and a double curvature surface, fibre orientations and in-plane shear angles change in the same manner for each different yarn. In order to predict the maximum shear reached on the single curvature surface, fibre orientation vectors available in the database are used. Maximum shear into the surface can be calculated by considering the various orientations of warp and weft vectors along the common edge, Figure 11. Understanding the effect of local orientations along connecting edges and is imperative to the algorithm in order to interpolate database results correctly.

Figure 11: Shear progression max shear angle

5 CONCLUSIONS

This work discusses initial stages in defining and building an algorithm that probes multiple draping scenarios using a universal database of base surface in-plane shear and fibre orientation results. A first version of the algorithm was developed using a simplified conical frustum featuring five geometric and four draping parameters. These nine parameters assisted in building a database of in-plane shear and fibre orientation results that the algorithm probes when building draping scenarios. Using edge lengths, radii and vertex coordinates found in CAD models of industrial moulds, the algorithm interpolates database results, linking base surfaces along common edges, and probes numerous draping scenarios until the best scenario, the strategy, is identified. Using individual base surfaces permits a greater number of draping scenarios to be probed than traditional simulation or trial and error techniques. Future work will involve using the full 12 parameter frustum, expanding the database, and allowing for more complex base surfaces such as twisted surfaces to be probed more accurately by the algorithm.

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